

A VISION OF DIGITAL INDIA: IT'S NEGATIVE & POSITIVE IMPACT ON INDIAN SOCIETY

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Abstract

It is a well-known incontrovertible fact that digital India is that the outcome of the many innovations and technological advancements. These transform the lives of people in many ways and will empower the society in a better manner. The 'Digital India' programme, an initiative of honorable Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi, will emerge new progressions in every sector. The motive behind the concept is to create participative, transparent and responsive system. The Digital India drive may be a dream project of the Indian Government to transform India into a knowledgeable economy and digitally empowered society, with good governance for citizens by bringing synchronization and coordination publicly accountability, digitally connecting and delivering the govt. programs and services to mobilize the potential of data technology across government departments.

Digital India program is an initiative to form technology access to every citizen of the country with a vision to rework India in to a digitally empowered state and a knowledge economy. Digital India program is citizen-centric and can change the system of delivery of services hence will change the standard of life. A Vision of Digital India Centered on 3 Key Areas –(i) Digital Infrastructure as a Utility to Every Citizen ,(ii) Governance & Services on Demand, (iii) Digital Empowerment of Citizens. Nine Pillars of Digital India program are the various areas like Broadband Highways, Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity, Electronics Manufacturing, e-Governance, Public Internet Access Program, e-Kranti, IT for Jobs, Information for all and Early Harvest Projects. Each Pillar has own challenges which we've to manage and overcome to form the program a successful mission.

Keyword: *Digital India, Positive Impact, Negative Impact, Challenges, etc*

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Introduction

Digital India is a program launched by the Government of India in order to ensure the Government's services are made available to public electronically by improved online infrastructure and by increasing high Internet connectivity or try to making the country digitally empowered within the field of information technology. The main motive of this program to connect rural areas with high-speed internet networks. Digital India consists of three core components: the event of universal digital literacy, secure and stable digital infrastructure & delivering government services digitally.

Launched on 1 -07-2015, by Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi, it's both enabler and beneficiary of other key Government of India schemes, like Make in India, Bharatnet, Startup India and Standup India, industrial corridors, Bharatmala, Sagarmala etc.

Digital India is an ambitious programme of state of India projected at Rs 1, 13,000 crores. This will be for preparing the India for the knowledge based transformation and delivering good governance to citizens by synchronized and coordinated engagement with both Central Government and government. This program has been under taking by of Electronics and Information Technology and will impact ministry of It & communication, ministry of rural development, ministry of human resource development, ministry of health and others. This program also will benefit all states and union territories. The vision of Digital India is to rework the country into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. It would also usher in public accountability through mandated delivery of government's services electronically.

1.1 Vision Of Digital India

The vision of Digital India is to change the country into a digitally empowered society and knowledge economy. It would make sure that government facilities are available to citizens digitally. A well digitally developed nation may be a prerequisite to a well-served nation. Once the remotest of the rural areas are digitally connected through high speed internet, then delivery of electronic government services to each citizen, targeted social advantages, and financial inclusion can be achieved in reality. One of the areas on which the vision of Digital India is centered is "Digital Infrastructure as a Utility to Each Citizen".

A key component under this plan is high speed internet as a core utility to facilitate online delivery of varied services. It is planned to line up enabling infrastructure for digital identity,

financial inclusion and ensure easy availability of common services centres. It is also important to supply citizens with “digital lockers” which might be sharable personal spaces on a public cloud and where documents issued by Government departments and agencies could be stored for easy online access. It is also planned to make sure that the cyberspace is formed safe and secure. The vision of digital India works on three keys, these are given below:

Table.1

S. No.	Digital Infrastructure as a Core Utility to Every Citizen	Governance & Services on Demand	Digital Empowerment of Citizens
1.	Availability of high speed internet as a core utility for delivery of services to citizens	Availability of services in real time from online & mobile platforms	Collaborative digital platforms for participative governance
2.	Easy access to a Common Service Centre	All citizen entitlements to be portable and available on the cloud	Universally accessible digital resource
3.	Shareable private space on a public cloud	Seamlessly integrated services across departments or jurisdictions	Universal digital literacy
4.	Safe and secure cyber-space	Digitally transformed services for improving ease of doing business	Availability of digital resources / services in Indian languages
5.	Mobile phone & bank account enabling citizen participation in digital & financial space	Making financial transactions electronic & cashless	Citizens not required to physically submit Govt. documents / certificates
6.	Cradle to grave digital identity that is unique, lifelong, online and authenticable to every citizen	Leveraging Geospatial Information Systems (GIS) for decision support systems & development	-----

Source: Self Structured

Digital India vision is an umbrella programme that covers government departments and ministries. It weaves together a large number of ideas and goals into a single, comprehensive vision so that each of them can be implemented as part of a larger goal. Digital India is to be implemented by the whole government with overall coordination being done by the Department of Electronics and Information Technology.

Digital India vision mainly works on nine pillars these are given below:

- (1) **Broadband Highways:** This pillar ensure to provide Broadband high speed network to rural areas as well as in urban areas and the National Information infrastructure will be build/restructured by DeitY.

- (2) **Universal Access to Mobile Connectivity:** To provide universal Mobile Connectivity “any time any where basis”.
- (3) **Public Internet Access Program:** Common service Centers (CSCs) will be made viable, multi- functional endpoints for service delivery. Post offices will be equipped as Multi Service Centers.
- (4) **e-Governance:** Reforming Government through Technology, Government Business Process Reengineering using IT to improve transactions by form simplification, reduction, online applications and tracking, Interface between departments, use of online repositories e.g school certificates, voter-ID cards etc. Integration of services and platforms e.g. payment gateway, Mobile Platform, Electronic Data Interchange, etc. Overall workflow automation inside government- e-office and workflow automation for citizen centric services.
- (5) **e-Kranti:** Ensures electronic delivery of services, expand mission mode projects using latest technologies and redesign/Re-engineer existing MMPs. Technology for e-Education to equip all schools with broadband, free wi-fi in schools & develop pilot Massive Online Opencourses MOOCs. Digital literacy program for citizens through common service centres. Technology for Health (e-Healthcare) –online medical consultation, online medicine supply and online medical records of patient. Technology for security- Mobile emergency services/alerts. Technology for Financial Inclusion- MMP Proposed under e-Kranti is Mobile banking, Micro ATM programme and CSCs. Technology for Justice- e-Courts, e-Police, e-Jails, eProsecution.
- (6) **Information to All:** Transparent, open Government by online hosting of information & documents-Citizens have, easy access to information. Government pro-activity engages through social media and web based platform to inform citizens, 2-way communication between citizens and government and online messaging to citizens on special occasions
- (7) **Electronic Manufacturing:** National Goal to expand domestic production –Target NET ZERO IMPORTS by 2020. specialise in a couple of big ticket items- set-top boxes, VSATs, medical equipment, smart cards, micro-ATMs, create economies of scale etc.
- (8) **IT Jobs:** Train people in smaller towns & villages for IT sector jobs & services. When the skill development of people in It sector done fully, then they will got job easily.

(9) **Early Harvest Programs:** IT platform for messages, Government greetings to be e-Greetings, Biometric attendance. Secure email within government, Wi-Fi in all Universities, standardize government email design, SMS based weather information, public wi-fi hotspots, disaster alerts, National Portal for Lost & Found children, Government Website upgradation etc.

Figure 1.0

1.2. Impact Of Digitalization

In present time internet comes under our daily needs, because we done our most of activities through online platform with the help of internet like- banking, online shopping, chatting, social media, reservations of ticket etc. From last three or four years online market rapidly increases day per day, there are lots of negative & positive impact of digitalization on human's life.

Negative Impact

Social Health: Digitalization connects us with more people over the web but it makes most folks only ready to speak out with the keyboard. Sitting at a restaurant looking around, more than 70% of the people will be on their mobile instead of companying the person next to them. Parents now a day couldn't speak much with their kids and complaining their kids are always

on the phone. What causes this to happen? Parents are showing a nasty example of twiddling with their phone over a meal and complaining next. With digitalization, it connects you with people globally but breaking our social skills right down to where communication can only be made through the utilization of the digital device. Change our habit, had everyone place their phone on the table at every meal and none is allowed to seem at it throughout the course of the meal. Let's defeat the negative impact of digitalization.

Physical Health: Technologies, like handheld tablets, smartphones, and computers, can hold a person's attention for long periods. This may lead to eyestrain. Eyestrain can also cause pains in other areas of the body, like the top, neck, or shoulders.

The way many of us use mobile devices and computers can also contribute to incorrect posture. Over time, this may lead to musculoskeletal issues.

Using technology too on the brink of bedtime may cause issues with sleep. This effect has got to do with the very fact that blue light, like the sunshine from cell phones, e-readers, and computers, stimulates the brain.

Most everyday digital technologies are sedentary. More extended use of those technologies promotes a more sedentary lifestyle, which is understood to possess negative health effects, like contributing to:

- Obesity
- Cardiovascular disease
- Type 2 diabetes
- Premature death
- Sleeping Problem

Mental Health: Mental health is another negative impact of digitalization. It causes distraction from your daily life. Always checking your phone for brand spanking new updates from social media, watching the phone to ascertain anyone messages you? This is a number of the distraction which will be caused by technology. They are not healthy for us.

Updating your social media frequently expecting regeneration or checking on the amount of such as you get from each post? This can cause depression once you aren't getting what you're expecting.

So many negative impacts on technology advancement and we have to learn where to draw a

line. Correct and build a positive habit to repel this negative impact from digitalization. It is not something people can stop you, to stop this you want to have the discipline to correct yourself.

Children Health: Children’s brains are still developing and should be more sensitive to the consequences of technology and its overuse than adult brains. Children who overuse technology could also be more likely to experience issues, including:

- Low academic performance & Creativity
- Lack of attention
- Delays in language, social and emotional development
- Physical inactivity and obesity
- Poor sleep quality & aggressive behaviour
- Social issues, such as social incompatibility and anxiety

Cyber Crime: In today’s era due to lack of security, various cyber-crimes have emerged in the past decade. Cyber security is thus an effort by users to stay their personal and professional information intact from the attacks on the internet. The main function of cyber security is to guard networks, computers, programs from unauthorized access and loss. Maximum numbers of users aren’t conscious of the risks and share their information unknowingly and their lack of knowledge makes them vulnerable to cyber-attacks.

2019 saw a big jump in cyber-crimes reported in India. Over 44.5 thousand cyber-crime incidents were registered in this year. Uttar Pradesh has a highest cyber-crime rate in India. Karnataka, followed suite that year. A majority of these cases were registered under the IT Act with the motive to sexually exploit victim. The northern part of Uttar Pradesh had very large number of cyber fraud in many fields as compared to other states. **Fig.1.2**

Positive Impact

Economic Impact: According to researcher, the Digital India program could boost GDP up to \$1 trillion by 2025. It can play an important role in macro-economic factors like employment generation, GDP growth, labour productivity, growth during a number of businesses and revenue leakages for the Indian Government. As per the planet Bank report, a tenth increase in mobile and broadband penetration increases the per capita GDP by 0.81% and 1.38% respectively within the developing countries. India is that the second world largest telecom market with approx. 915 million wireless subscribers. There is still a huge economic opportunity in India as the tele density in rural areas. India is only 45% where more than 65% of the population lives. Future growth of telecommunication industry in terms of variety of subscribers is expected to return from rural areas as urban areas are saturated with a tele-density of quite 160%.

Social Impact: Social sectors like health care, education & banking are unable to succeed in bent the citizens thanks to obstructions and limitations like middleman, ignorance, illiteracy, poverty, information, lack of funds & investments. These challenges have led to an imbalanced growth within the rural areas with marked differences within the social and economic station of the people in these areas. Modern ICT makes it easier for people to get access to resources & services. The penetration of mobile devices could also be very useful as a complementary channel to public service delivery aside from the creation of entirely new services which can have a huge impact on the standard of lifetime of the users and cause social modernization. The poor literacy rate in India is thanks to unavailability of physical infrastructure in rural and remote areas. This is where m-Education services can play a crucial role by reaching remote masses.

According to estimates, the digital literacy in India is just 6.5% and the internet penetration is 20.83 out of 100 populations. The Digital India project are going to be helpful in providing real-time education and partly address the challenge of lack of teachers within the education system through smart and virtual classrooms.

Environmental Impact: The major changes within the technology space won't only brought changes to the financial system but also will contribute to the environmental changes. The next generation technologies will help in reducing the carbon footprint & fuel consumption, waste

management, greener workplaces and thus resulting in a greener ecosystem. The ICT sector helps in efficient management and usage of scarce and non-renewable resources. Cloud computing technology minimizes carbon emissions by improving mobility and adaptability. The energy consumption are often decreased from 201.8 terawatt hour (TWh) in 2010 to 139.8 TWh in 2020 by higher adoption of cloud data centers causing a 28% reduction in carbon footprint from 2010

Education Impact: Digital media has become a strong means of connecting, communicating, creating, and learning among students. Internet of things (IoT) has radically transformed the condition of education within the country over the past few years. Digitalization has brought in modern methods of teaching inside and out of doors the school rooms. Technology within the 21st century is bringing dramatic changes in our lives.

Growth of exponential technologies like AI, nanotechnology, robotics, etc. is bringing good impact on the evolution of education. These growth drivers also are changing employment dynamics as new skills and understanding are required to satisfy the longer term demands of the work industry. That is why educational institutes are compelled to include digitization within the learning process to impart critical thinking, innovation, collaboration and problem-solving traits in students.

Fig. 1.3

1.3 Challenges For Digital India

Few of the challenges faced in the successful implementation of Digital India Programme are:

- Financial and technical issues
- Attitude of citizens as well as government personnel
- Lack of infrastructure and required technology
- Lack of education
- Cyber-crimes and Lack of confidence
- Training needs

2. Review Of Literature

- (Jibril, Kwarteng, Pilik, Botha, & Osakwe, 2020) examined the factors towards adoption of the online business in the developing countries like Ghana, where there is low penetration of internet.
- Rita., 2019, explained the reason for research on e-service quality and customer satisfaction on customer behavior in online shopping to understand the most important dimensions of e-service quality that have impact on customer satisfaction, customer trust, and customer behaviour, building on existing literature on e-service quality in online shopping.
- (Sayyed Arbaina, 2018) stated that sports and physical exercises have gotten one of the most significant components of human life as it adds to both mental and physical wellness. Today individuals are exceptionally associated with sports exercises to assemble group spirit, mental quality, certainty and dynamic
- Digital marketing communication has exerted one of the strongest influences over the consumer buying decision process (Gay et al. 2007). Consumer buying decision process can be understood with the help of five stages decision making steps including need recognition, search for information, evaluation of alternatives, selection and purchase and post purchase behavior (Kollat et al. 1970).
- Digital marketing communication offers fragmented attention to the audience. Rather than aiming at masses, this productive medium interacts with individual target audience with their preferred channel (Wind and Mahajan, 2002) and establishes a dialogue rather than a monologue.

- Ferrar (2010) in his study attributed cost effectiveness of digital media as the most important driver that replaced expensive and less measurable traditional media. Charan and Jaiswal (2012) in their study concerning mobile banking stated that internet has emerged as the cheapest medium of communication.

3. Need Of The Study

The proliferation of developments in digital technology makes choosing the proper method of digitizing resources an increasingly complex process for information organizations. This technology may be a key way forward within the twenty-first century, but it's important to develop a technique to assess fully the prices and benefits of going ahead with a digitization. In the current state of technology, digitizing from the primary gives a much better reproduction quality for colour material and material with weak contrasts than digitizing from film. In present we seen that human being fully depend on internet or social media, physical work is decrease rapidly. So in this study we try to explain problems related from humans beings regarding his activities on online platform.

4. Objective Of The Study

- To study the present status of digitalization in India.
- To identify the various service provided by government of India through digital mode.
- To analyse people awareness about vision of digitalization in negative as well as positive aspects.

5. Hypothesis

On the basis of objectives mentioned above, the researcher would like to test the following null hypothesis.

H01 There is no significant impact of digitalization on changing status of human's life style in India.

H02 There is no significant effect about human being awareness in various vision of digitalization

H03 There is no significant impact of government on vision of digital India.

6. Research Methodology

The study is based on the primary as well as secondary data. For the analysis of changing structure of digital India, a Primary Survey will be conducted using self-structured

questionnaire and face to face discussion. The types of question to be asked will be both pen-ended and closed-ended. To test the validity and veracity of the structure of questionnaire and to find out whether the purpose will be fulfilled a pilot study will be conducted with a sample of 10-12 questions.

7. Conclusion

A vision of digital India can help in improving economic & social condition of human beings through development of highly developed internet network system, activities apart from providing access to health, education, banking, social networking services etc.

However, it is important to note vision of digital India alone cannot directly lead to overall development of our country. The overall development & growth can be realized through enhancing and supporting elements such as literacy, employment basic infrastructure, overall business environment, regulatory environment, etc.

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